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ASSESSMENT. FORMATIVE AND SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT. THEIR INTRODUCTION AND USE IN PRACTISE

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ABSTRACT

This article states about assessment, formative and summative assessment. It also says regarding the introduction of the assessment types as well as their usage in education. Moreover, it explores how these assessment types are being used in schools instead of traditional assessment methods, and whether the new assessment types have brought achievements or not

In today's world, education plays an essential role in leading humanities to bright life. With the help of education, people can achieve their main goals in life and find a suitable desired profession. One of the main parts that determine the effectiveness of the education is the assessment system. Assessment is regarded as one of the vital key aspect to determine learner's expertise, skills and even lack of knowledge. There are a number of views regarded assessment. To start with the notion emphasized by Komil Jolilov: "Assessment is the process of measuring the level of formation of any domain (a set of knowledge, skills, and competencies) in learners (test takers)" [1;10]. We can see such views of some scientists about how to evaluate pupils. According to Mark Wilson and Kathleen Scalise "Effective assessment methods can play a powerful role in the learning process—for example, it can elevate an average student to the top three in the class—but only if certain conditions are met. Student assignments must be relevant or relevant to learning objectives, and students must receive meaningful and timely feedback on their performance as well as perform targeted work. To manage their learning effectively, students need to understand three things: (a) how they are to be assessed, (b) where they are at, and (c) how they can improve." [2;635].

Moreover, we can see other definitions about assessment. For example, in oxford dictionary the notion assessment stands for "the process of testing students and making judgments about their knowledge, ability, and progress" and in Cambridge dictionary we can come across the notion "the act of judging or deciding the amount, value, quality, or importance of something, or the judgment or decision that is made". In agreement with these points, we consider assessment as a process of measuring the level of achievement of educational goals at a certain stage of the educational process, determining and analyzing the results based on predetermined criteria, and this process provides us with information on the acquired

knowledge. enables the systematic collection, analysis and use of data. Because the assessment system is considered a feedback system in the field of education, it creates an opportunity to directly observe the results of education, conduct monitoring, choose teaching tactics in education, and form the principle of development in students.

Nowadays, in Uzbekistan, at most schools, pupils are evaluated with "2", "3", "4", "5" points as a traditional assessment methods. In this numbers, "5" is for the best learners, "4" is for good learners, "3" is for bad learners, and "2" is for the worst learners who is lack of knowledge. In addition to that some scientists claim that new forms of evaluation should be used in education based on 21st century standards. For example, Australian scholars Patrick Griffey and Esther Care argue that "Traditional forms of assessment may not be suitable for testing many twenty-first century skills, particularly skills that may be considered non-cognitive". [3;7] We also support this idea, because today we not only increase the knowledge level of our learners, but also develop their skills and abilities such as communication, working with others, creativity, critical thinking, team management, problem solving, use of technology and so on. , and we will certainly appreciate it.

Currently, changes are taking place in all areas of our society, rapid development is taking place to meet world standards. Such changes can also be found in the education system. On December 24, 2021, the head of our state signed two historic decisions on granting independence in financial, academic and organizational management to family educational institutions, which will lead to fundamental positive changes in the family education system. This, in turn, requires a new system-based approach to the management of higher education institutions. Constantly monitoring the quality of education and the level of knowledge of students is the basis for introducing important innovations into the educational process. Today, based on the new system, various forms of assessment have been developed and are being presented to the educational process. These are formative and summative assessments.

Formative assessment is used during the term at schools. Formative assessment provides feedback and information during the instructional process, while learning is taking place, and while learning is occurring. Formative assessment measures student progress but it can also assess your own progress as an instructor. Formative assessment attempts to provide feedback to both teachers and students about student performance and learning. This is a process that monitors the needs and progress of students during the learning process. The main task of the formative assessment is to determine whether the requirements for this academic year have been met or not. Some scientists give their thoughts about this assessment type. For instance, Marina Aleksandrovna Pinskaya, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, researcher writes the following in her book "New Forms of Assessment": "Formative assessment is necessary to diagnose how the educational process goes not only at the final stage, but also at the initial and intermediate stages, and if the data turns out to be unsatisfactory, based on the obtained data, changes can be made to include the necessary data and improve the quality of educational activities. Formative assessment focuses on individual learning skills or skills within a curriculum rather than the curriculum as a whole. These assessments are designed to measure progress toward a specific goal" [4]. And Dilnoza Okhunova quotes: "Formative assessments are easy to create, easy to take, easy to collect and easy to use the results. In addition, they

require a limited amount of time to complete. Formative assessment helps students set individual goals and track progress on a daily basis" [5,2]. In agreement with these points, we can say that formative assessment is one of the fruitful way of determining pupil's achievements at the end of term.

Summative assessment is used at the end of the term at schools. Summative assessment means student assessment; it is result oriented. This is part of the evaluation process given to participants periodically, usually at the end of a course, term or unit. The goal is to check the knowledge of the students, that is, to check how well they have learned the material taught by them. Khusanova Nafisa Burkhanovna, Adilova Sadokat Nurillayevna in their article "Summative and formative evaluation system" write the following: "Summative evaluation seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of a lesson or program, examines the educational process, etc. Scores, points, or percentages obtained as indicators of the quality of the curriculum and provide a basis for ranking schools. The main purpose of summative assessment is to evaluate the final results or achievements of students or educational programs. It allows to evaluate the effectiveness of teaching and learning processes in general. Summative assessment is usually conducted at the end of a course, semester or academic year. Summative assessment has several main features. First of all, these assessment methods help to study the level of knowledge acquired by students. Students will have the opportunity to test themselves, evaluate their knowledge, and support what they have learned during the learning process. Second, summative assessment allows students to compare their results. This characterization makes it possible to compare students to each other, to determine the level of knowledge acquired by students, and to compare educational programs" [6,50-51]. We can realize from this notion that summative assessment helps pupils enhance their creativeness as well as thoughts. In addition, projects and portfolios are also used as a form of summative assessment. Projects are scientific, practical or experimental works prepared by students, which allow students to demonstrate their acquired knowledge and skills. Portfolios include handouts, proposals, notes, assignments, and other materials prepared by students. These portfolios help to assess student learning, development, and achievement.

Let's look through the difference between the two kinds of assessment in the following:

1. Formative assessment is used during the term and summative assessment is used at the end of the term;
2. Formative assessment is an assessment for learning, summative is for education;
3. Formative assessment is carried out monthly or during the term, summative is used only at the end of the term;
4. Formative assessment is used to raise learner's expertise, summative is used for assessing learner's activity.

These two kinds of assessment are key aspects of enhancing education at schools. The reason for this is that nowadays, numerous schools are using in practice the new assessment types. From this experience, teachers have realized that instead of traditional evaluation, the new assessment form have helped teachers determine achievement and lack of knowledge among pupils more clearly. And one of the best side of the process of practicing the new assessment forms for teachers at schools is that there is 10,20,30,40 percent of salary bonus for

teachers. This salary bonus is given to schools where the evaluation form is used successfully. On condition that we see some foreign countries' assessment standards, for example in UK, there is a reward called "TAQA" for teachers who evaluate pupils in a correct and fair way.

In conclusion, we can realize that assessment is one of the vital way to enhance educational system.

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